

ARE INFORMATION BIAS AND FREE RIDING IN CONTINGENT VALUATION SURVEY INEVITABLE? EVIDENCE FROM THE DIBRU SAIKHOWA NATIONAL PARK, ASSAM

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ABSTRACT

Contingent valuation method (CVM) is used to measure the value of non-market goods. As a stated preference technique, CVM functions under a constructed hypothetical market which enables people to express their preferences directly for a good. However, because of this hypothetical market, CVM estimates are often criticised on the ground of being affected by a set of biases. Yet, studies in favour of CVM are also plenty in number. The credit can mostly be attributed to the method's unique ability to measure both use and non-use values. The current study seeks to test for the presence of information bias and free riding behaviour in CVM responses in the context of a valuation programme for the Dibru Saikhowa National park in Assam. It also aims to investigate whether or not such anomalies can be corrected, if found any. The study adopts a complete non-parametric approach to fulfill the objectives and concludes that with appropriate precautions and corrective measures the aforesaid flaws can be avoided.

Key words: Information bias, Free riding, Willingness to pay, Open ended elicitation, Dichotomous choice elicitation.

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1. Introduction:

The Contingent Valuation Method (CVM) is a stated preference technique for estimating the economic value of non-market¹ goods. The entire premise for stated preference technique arises from the failure of the conventional market to estimate the demand for resources with sizeable non-use values, for example environmental resources (Kolstad, 2006). Non-use value covers situations in which individuals who do not make use, or intend to make use, of any given good or asset or attribute would nevertheless feel a loss in utility if such things were to disappear (Turner, 2001). People's concern about destruction of diverse ecosystems or endangered species in remote parts of the world, without having an intention to visit or see them, is an example of non-use value. In cases like these, people value a good not being connected with its use by themselves. So their own behaviours in conventional market do not signal about their preferences for these goods. Inability to extract these preferences, by observing how people behave in markets with actual transactions however, does not simply imply these preferences are zero. Rather, it implies that the market in which these preferences can be tracked itself is *missing or non-existent*. Stated preference methods like CVM solve this issue by constructing this missing market. It involves asking people directly to state their preferences for a good in concern, in terms of a price to get an additional amount of the good or in terms of a compensation to go without it, in the set up of a hypothetical market where the good was getting transacted. It is hence, able to extract proxies for the non-use values, where no other observable data is available.

The question that often arises is 'why to take the trouble of constructing a non-existent market for estimating these non use values?' The answer lies in the very core of economic decision making process that aims to achieve the goal of 'optimal allocation of scarce resources to maximise utility'. What signals scarcity in economics is the price of a good. If environmental goods are not valued explicitly, they will anyhow be valued implicitly through policy decisions. As the decision makers are often not aware that they make these valuations, this procedure produces an arbitrary and inconsistent set of prices (Navrud, 2001). For example, the nominal (or sometimes zero) entrance fee to access a natural site. Prices so determined do not reflect the true scarcity (both in terms of quantity and quality) of the good in concern. This is a classic case where price fails as a signal of scarcity, making the good seemingly abundant, and hence indirectly contributing to its indiscriminate

¹ Goods with positive utility but cannot be bought and sold in the conventional market.

exploitation and degradation. A proper estimation of total value (use + non use) can prevent this under pricing and this is where CVM comes into play. Estimation of use values can also be attempted through revealed preference methods, but in case of non-use values, revealed preference methods do not work (as yet again, the market in which preferences would be revealed does not exist). This explains the requirement for CVM and the constructed hypothetical market since there is hardly any other market available.

Although complete in terms of its ability to measure total value, CVM often has to face a hoard of criticisms. A number of biases and a few other problems associated with the hypothetical nature of the constructed market are central to those. *Information bias and free riding* are two such anomalies that may produce biased results in case of CVM. Information bias results because CVM responses are often believed to be sensitive to the level of information provided to the surveyed individuals. Exaggerated information thus can produce a bias in the estimated value. Free riding on the other hand, can underestimate the true value since respondents will not be revealing their true preference pattern for the good and will want to free ride on other's contribution. In both these cases the true preference will not be estimated. Hence, it is pertinent for a CVM result to be free of these flaws. The present study intends to test for the influence of these two anomalies in the willingness to pay (WTP) of the people, elicited through CVM for estimating the preservation value of the Dibru Saikhowa National Park (DSNP) in Assam, India. Although it is necessary to check for these factors whenever CVM is applied, very few studies are there, especially in the Indian valuation literature that have methodologically addressed these issues. The study also seeks to investigate whether or not these flaws can be corrected, if found at all, by adopting appropriate measures.

2. Study Area:

The Dibru-Saikhowa National Park was created in 1999 by merging the Dibru and Saikhowa Reserve Forests. The 340 sq km area is spread over the districts of Dibrugarh and Tinsukia. Initially declared as a sanctuary, its status was upgraded to a National Park for the conservation of the White Winged Wood Duck (*Asarcornis scutulata*), the state bird of Assam. The bird is currently in the IUCN red list of threatened species due to its small and fragmented population of only around 1000 all over the globe, out of which India homes around 450 (Birdlife International, 2017). While Assam and Arunachal Pradesh are the two prime habitats of the bird in India, Dibru Saikhowa is its main stronghold. Sheltering over

500 species of birds, DSNP has been declared an Important Bird Area (IBA) by BNHS (Bombay Natural History Society) and Bird Life International². The major attractions in the park are the feral horses, tiger, elephant, wild buffalo, the Indo Gangetic dolphins, hoolock gibbon, capped langur and slow loris. The park is the only protected area in the entire north-east with the feral horses. The rich floral diversity of the park is represented by 43 species of orchids. The park was declared as a Biosphere Reserve under the aegis of United Nation's *Man and Biosphere* programme. It is one of the 19 biodiversity hotspots in the world³ and is considered to be the only river island National Park in the country and the largest Salix Swamp forest in the entire north-east. The park also happens to be the second largest river island in the state of Assam, after 'Majuli'.

The park is currently burdened with a lot of problems. Human settlement inside the park, presence of a huge cattle population and the consequent over grazing, deforestation, flood, illegal timber felling, stuff crunch, heavy resource dependency of the nearby fringe villagers on the protected area are worth mentioning among others⁴. It is often debated that the conservation policies of the government of India pertaining to the state of Assam are mainly rhino centric with a recent focus being shifted to tiger reserves. Other equally valuable natural areas are somewhat lagging behind from the point of view of receiving desired government attention. Hence, there is the need for a valuation study of the park to estimate its preservation value for the population of Assam.

3. Conceptual Framework:

3.1 Information Bias: CVM involves construction of a hypothetical market. While giving the respondents the context of this market, the researcher has to describe the good that is supposed to get transacted and for which the respondents have to express their WTP. The description of the good means a certain set of information that the researcher supplies to the respondents. If the supplied information prejudices the individual's bid, information bias occurs. It may also result from defects in questionnaire design (Thayer,

² (as found in <http://natureconservation.in/dibru-saikhowa-national-park-complete-detail-updated/> accessed on 10/08/2019)

³ (as found in <http://natureconservation.in/dibru-saikhowa-national-park-complete-detail-updated/> accessed on 10/08/2019)

⁴ (as found in *The Incredible Dibru Saikhowa National Park*, published by the Dibru Saikhowa Conservation Society)

1981). Now if supplied information really prejudices the individual's bid, WTPs associated with higher levels of information are supposed to be different from WTPs associated with lower levels of information. Keeping this in mind, the present study seeks to test for the presence of information bias in the respondents' WTP by comparing between two sub groups who received two different levels of information about DSNP.

3.2 Free Riding: Free riding is the problem associated with public good provision resulting from the incentive for an individual to understate his preference for the public good in the hope of obtaining the good at a lower cost (Maddala and Miller, 2004). Free riding thus results in underestimation of the true WTP. The study seeks to test for the presence of free riding behaviour by comparing the WTP of respondents who have chosen Tax, as a payment vehicle with that of those who have chosen Voluntary Contribution (VC).

3.3 Willingness to Pay: Willingness to pay (WTP) is a measure of welfare in CVM that has been used in this study. It is the maximum amount of income a person will pay in exchange for an improvement in circumstances, or the maximum amount a person will pay to avoid a decline in circumstances (Haab and McConnell, 2003). Another alternative to WTP is the Willingness to Accept (WTA) which stands for the minimum amount of compensation a person will accept for a decline in circumstances, or the minimum amount a person will accept to forego an improvement in circumstances (Haab and McConnell, 2003). The present study has chosen WTP over WTA, since WTP estimates are empirically found stable in repeated trials (Coursey et al. 1987).

3.4 Open Ended Elicitation Method: In this method, the respondent faces a direct question asking how much they are willing to pay for the proposed plan for a good in concern. The respondent is free to state any value in answer according to their preference for the good. The key reason for choosing this method in the study is, it provides a specific welfare number in terms of the stated value for each survey respondent (Freeman III et.al, 2014) and hence is useful for analysing the individual motivations working behind the willingness to pay. Other methods lack this characteristic.

3.5 Single Bounded Dichotomous Choice Elicitation: It is a close ended method where respondents don't get to say the amount they are willing to pay explicitly. Rather, they face a single question asking 'Are you willing to pay X?', where X varies across the sample (Bateman et.al, 2001). The study has chosen this method because of its two important characteristics. First, it provides a relatively familiar context to people. People get involved in day-to-day transactions offered on a take-it-or-leave-it basis, where they have to decide

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whether or not to purchase the good at the offered price. *Secondly*, it is a relatively simple decision problem since only a yes/no answer is required. This results in lower levels of item non-response and unit non-response (Freeman III et.al, 2014).

4. Objectives and Research Question:

4.1 Objectives:

1. To test for the presence of information bias in the WTP responses.
2. To test for the presence of free riding behaviour in the WTP responses.

4.2 Research Question: The study intends to seek the answer for the following research question;

Is it inevitable for the WTP responses received via CVM to be affected by information bias and free riding?

5. Methodology:

5.1 Data source: The principal work of the present study is based on primary data. The required data have been collected from three districts in the state of Assam with structured interview schedule.

Some relevant secondary data have also been used specifically related to the study area. The data have been collected from the office of the Divisional Forest Officer- Tinsukia Wildlife Division, District Census Handbook-Census of India (2011), official websites of Birdlife International (www.birdlife.org), International Union for Conservation of Nature (www.iucn.org), Nature Conservation (www.natureconservation.in) etc.

5.2 Sampling Design: The study follows a multi stage sampling design. Results of CVM studies in empirical literature are often claimed to have a 'Distance Decay' effect i.e., people's preferences for a good decrease with the increase in the distance from it. Keeping this in mind, selection of the districts in the first stage of sampling has been done on the basis of geographical proximity criterion. At first, the shortest road distance from the study area to the district headquarters of all the 27 districts of Assam (as per census 2011) has been listed. In the next step, all the districts of the respective district headquarters have been arranged in ascending order of distance and divided into three equal categories, each

containing 9 districts. Thus, the first category contains 9 such districts that are the nearest to the study site and the third category contains 9 districts that are farthest to the study site. The 9 districts in the second or the median category fall in between the two. After that, 1 district from each category has been selected at random. The districts so selected are Tinsukia from the first, Nagaon from the second and Bongaigaon from the third category. In the second stage, one revenue circle from each district has been selected. The circles are Tinsukia from Tinsukia district, Kaliabor from Nagaon district and Sidli (Part II) from Bongaigaon district. In the next stage, out of all the villages/towns listed under the revenue circles, 2 villages/towns have been selected from each. These are Tinsukia town and Bordubi from Tinsukia revenue circle, Jakhalabandha and Silghat from Kaliabor revenue circle and BRPL township and Dhaligaon from Sidli (Part) revenue circle. At the final stage, a total of 362 households have been selected trying to include almost equal numbers of households from each village/town into the final sample. The figures are: 61 households from Tinsukia, 60 from Bordubi, 60 each from Jakhalabandha and Silghat, 61 from BRPL township and 60 from Dhaligaon. Multi stage random sampling has been applied from the stage of district selection to the final stage of household selection. The primary unit of observation is the household and data have been collected from the head of the household. In case the head of the household was not available, any other member from the household, above 18 years of age, having the capability of taking decisions for the household has been interacted with.

6. Results and Analysis:

6.1 Comparison of WTP between two sub-groups receiving different levels of information: To test for the presence of information bias in the surveyed responses, the WTP of two sub groups receiving different levels of information has been compared. To reach this goal, the technique of split-sampling⁵ has been applied. All the respondents were classified into two groups viz. Group A and Group B. Group A is called the *control group* and Group B is called the *treatment group*. Selection of respondents into groups has been done by getting them to choose one from two identical lottery chits offered, (without telling them the difference between the two) before starting the actual survey. If the respondent had

⁵ Researchers using split-sampling experiments are usually interested in determining the difference on outcomes such as survey statistics or other evaluative characteristics between the two groups. The sample is randomly divided into two halves and each half receives a different treatment. (Lavrakas, 2008)

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chosen chit A, his/her household has been included into the *control group* and if he/she has chosen chit B, his/her household has been included into the *treatment group*. In this way, out of 362 respondents, 185 were added to the control group and 177 were added to the treatment group. This shows that the selection process was fairly random which is necessary for ensuring the internal validity of the experiment (Lavrakas, 2008).

The information provided to the control group is regarded as the base level information. The base level information contains a description about the current status and problems of DSNP. The treatment group received the base level information, plus an additional layer of information (*treatment*) which was separately read out to them. The additional information contains some specifics that back the base information but is believed to be not so essential for valuing the park i.e., a brief socio-economic profile of the villagers of the two villages inside the park (based on data from secondary sources). The final sample size for testing information bias has to be reduced to 339 excluding the protest bids⁶. To identify the protest bids, at first the number of respondents who said 'no' to the initial question (Would you be willing to pay a part of your monthly household income to implement the proposed preservation plan for DSNP, as it has just been described, for a period of five years?) has been calculated. A total of 36 such respondents were found. These respondents during the survey were asked to state their principal reason for not paying by getting to choose from a given list of possible reasons. These are shown in table 1.

Table 1: Reasons for not willing to pay

Sl. No.	Reasons
1	I cannot afford to contribute due to my limited income.
2	The park is of no importance to me and hence I do not value its preservation.
3	I am not happy with the proposed preservation plan.
4	Preservation of nature is the responsibility of the government.
5	I believe this questionnaire is not the best approach to look at this issue.
6	I am not happy about the payment vehicles.

Source: Author's compilation

⁶ Protest bids occur whenever individuals who oppose or do not approve of the survey or some part of it, fail to respond or place a zero value on a good that they actually value (Halstead, 1992).

All those respondents who have chosen any of the options from 3 to 6 were identified as protest bidders (23 in total) and excluded from the sample. However, respondents choosing either option 1 or 2 were included into the sample (13 in total). This explains the sample size of 339. Out of the 339, 163 were from the control group and 176 were from the treatment group.

To find out if there is any difference between the WTP of the control and the treatment group, two separate statistical methods were applied for treating the dichotomous choice responses and the open ended responses.

6.1.1 Dichotomous Choice responses: The DC responses were first put to test since the DC question comes before the open ended question in the questionnaire and this logical sequence was important to maintain for the study. DC responses are 'yes / no' responses where the respondents were asked to state whether they will pay the offered bid or not. One bid was offered at random to each respondent from a range of bids with bid values Rs. 20, Rs. 50, Rs. 100, Rs. 200 and Rs. 500. For designing the optimal range of bids, a pilot survey was conducted involving 42 households selected at random. DC choice questions in the pilot survey were avoided. Rather, an open ended question (what is your maximum willingness to pay for the proposed preservation plan for DSNP?) was asked to get a fair idea of the possible distribution of the WTP. The minimum value of WTP in the pilot survey was found to be Rs. 30 with a frequency of 2 (4.8% of total) and the maximum value was found to be Rs. 400 with a frequency of 1 (2.4% of total). While designing the range of bids for the final survey, these factors have been taken into consideration. A bid range with 5 bids has been constructed. The first bid was fixed at a lower level than the realised minimum bid in the pilot survey, to allow for more coverage, keeping in mind that the final sample size will be many times higher than the pilot sample. Hence, the first bid has been set at Rs. 20. The second bid has been set at Rs. 50, since this amount received the highest frequency of 7 (16.7% of total) in the pilot survey among all the values smaller than the mode. The third bid which is also the central bid in the 5 point bid scale, has been set at Rs. 100 which was also the mode of the WTP distribution in the pilot survey with the highest frequency of 12 (28.6% of total). The fourth bid was set at Rs. 200. This amount received the highest frequency of 6 (14.3% of total) in the pilot survey among all the values greater than the mode. The fifth and the last bid was set at a higher level than the realised maximum bid in the pilot survey again to allow for more coverage. Hence, the last bid is Rs. 500. Figure 1 is a graphic representation of the number of respondents reporting 'yes' to the offered bids:

Figure 1: Line graph representing the number of 'yes' responses to the offered bids:

Source: Author's computation from field survey

The line graph in figure 1 shows that the number of 'yes' responses to the offered bid is almost declining with the increase in the bid values (the only exception is the movement from Rs. 20 to Rs. 50). This proves that the bid range created for the study roughly falls in line with the demand law (which states, whenever price of a good increases, its demand falls) and hence signals that apart from a minor mishappening, the constructed bid range is consistent with economic theory. Here demand is represented by the 'yes' responses since by agreeing to pay the price (offered bid), people are showing their demand for an improvement in DSNP.

Going by the popular definition of information bias, the group with access to additional information i.e., the treatment group has a higher probability of saying 'yes' than their counterparts. Or in other words, there is supposed to be a difference in the distribution of responses between the two groups in the presence of information bias.

Table 2: Distribution of responses to offered bids between Group A and Group B

Answer Type (Response to offered bids)	Group		Total
	A (Control)	B (Treatment)	
Yes	108 [44.4%] (66.3%)	135 [55.6%] (76.7%)	243 [100%]
No	55 [57.3%] (33.7%)	41 [42.7%] (23.3%)	96 [100%]
Total	163 (100%)	176 (100%)	339

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

Note: Figures within [.] and (.) are percentages within Answer type and Group respectively

Table 2 tells us that out of a total of 243 'yes' responses, 135 (55.6%) are from the treatment group and 108 (44.4%) are from the control group. Again, within the treatment group 76.7% responded 'yes' whereas, within the control group only 66.3% responded 'yes'. This indicates towards the presence of a difference. However, the table cannot detect if this difference is statistically significant. To test for the presence of statistically significant difference between the two groups, a Pearson chi square test has been run. Pearson chi square has been selected since the data is ordinal in nature (Nunes, 2002) and do not meet the requirements for a parametric testing procedure. Now, we need to see whether the null hypothesis of no difference gets retained (no information bias) or rejected (information bias).

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H₀: There is no significant difference in the distribution of responses between Group A and Group B.

After running the test, the results obtained are displayed in table 3.

Table 3: Chi-Square Test results with responses and Group

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	4.550	1	0.033
N of Valid Cases	339		

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

The test result rejects the null hypothesis at 5% level of significance and confirms the presence of information bias. This means that WTP is sensitive to the level of information delivered and the additional information provided to the treatment group affected their WTP. However, CV responses are often claimed to be affected by hypothetical bias. In stated preference valuation surveys, hypothetical bias can be defined as the difference between what a person indicates they would pay in a hypothetical situation and what a person would actually pay in a real situation (List and Gallet, 2001, Loomis, 2014). One of the principal causes for hypothetical bias is that people tend to forget about the constraints on their ability to pay in a hypothetical situation. To correct or minimise any possible hypothetical bias that may be present in this study, an ex-post method of correction has been adopted. This is known as 'uncertainty recoding' (Loomis, 2014). Before applying this method, the respondents who reported 'yes' to the initial offered bid, were given a reality check by getting reminded about three important things that are listed in the box below:

- Please keep in mind that, DSNP is not the only protected area in Assam. Think about the nearest national park/sanctuary to you apart from DSNP, which may also be in need of assistance.
- Please keep in mind that, your income is limited.
- Think about your current household expenses. To contribute to this protection plan, you have to cut down your current expenditure from one or more heads in your household budget.

After the reality check, the following certainty question was asked to the respondents :

Q: How sure/certain are you that you will actually contribute the above amount on a scale of "1" to "10", where "1" is "Very Uncertain" and "10" is "Very Certain"? (Please circle one response)

Very Uncertain											Very Certain
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10		

'Yes' responses against which a certainty score of 7 or more were received were retained as 'yes', whereas others were converted into 'no'. Empirical evidences support that corrected 'yes' responses with this benchmark of 7 matches actual cash payments in experimental markets really well (Blumenschein et al., 2008; Ethier et al., 2000; Morrison and Brown, 2009). The corrected responses are called HB (hypothetical bias) corrected responses.

Figure 2: Line graph representing number of HB corrected 'yes' responses to offered bids:

Source: Author's computation from field survey

Figure 2 shows that, in comparison to the initial 'yes' responses, the distribution of HB corrected 'yes' responses is a better representation of the demand law since the number of 'yes' decreases with every increase in the bid value (comparison is made with figure 1). This justifies the reality check and the process of hypothetical bias correction.

Table 4: Distribution of HB corrected responses to offered bids between Group A and Group B

Answer Type (HB corrected responses)	Group		Total
	A (Control)	B (Treatment)	
Yes	89 [50.9%] (54.6%)	86 [49.1%] (48.9%)	175 [100%]
No	74 [45.1%] (45.4%)	90 [54.9%] (51.1%)	164 [100%]
Total	163 (100%)	176 (100%)	339

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

Figures within [.] and (.) are percentages within Answer type and Group respectively

From table 4 it is evident that, after the reality check the total number of 'yes' responses have decreased considerably from 243 (as reported in table 2) to 175. In case of the control group, it has declined from 108 to 89, whereas in case of the treatment group it has declined from 135 to 86. This indicates the effectiveness of the reality check. However, it appears that the reality check is more effective in case of the treatment group. When we look at the distribution of the new HB corrected responses, out of a total of 175 'yes' responses, the share of the treatment group is now 49.1% and that of the control group is 50.9%. Within Group, the treatment group now has 48.9% 'yes' sayers, whereas, the control group has 54.6% 'yes' sayers. So, the distribution seems more on the equal side in comparison to table 2. This may be because of the fact that although additional information might somehow had an effect on the initial WTP of the respondents, that effect wore off after the process of realty check and hypothetical bias correction. However this can only be confirmed after performing the chi square test between the two groups again, with HB corrected responses.

Table 5: Chi-Square Test results with HB corrected responses and Group

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.116	1	0.291
N of valid cases	339		

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

Table 5 reveals that, the test fails to reject the null hypothesis of no difference and confirms that hypothetical bias corrected responses of the two groups are not significantly different from one another. This calls for an important argument in the study. Although it appeared that information bias might be initially present in the study, after correction of hypothetical bias i.e., after the reality check has been introduced, it has lost its strength. This implies that additional information alone is not strong enough to influence the WTP responses in a CVM study. The fact that the market is hypothetical and not real, magnifies the information bias. Hence, adopting proper measures for minimising hypothetical bias can also minimise information bias.

6.2.2 Open Ended Responses: DC responses do not give us the exact value of the Maximum Willingness to Pay (MWTP) of the surveyed respondents. Hence, after taking the DC responses, a direct open ended question was asked to the respondents to get the exact MWTP values. Since the respondents can state any value that may represent their preference levels, MWTP values so received represent a continuous variable. Presence of difference in these MWTP values between the control and the treatment group has been tested with Mann-Whitney U test keeping in mind the continuous nature of the data. The Mann-Whitney U test is considered as the non-parametric equivalent to independent sample t test (Nachar, 2008). An independent sample t test is used see if there is any significant difference between the means of two samples, whereas in Mann-Whitney U test, rather than comparing the means of two samples, we compare the means of the ranks assigned to the values of these two samples. In case of a statistically significant difference, most of the smaller ranks will go to the values of one sample and most of the higher ranks will go the values of the other sample (Gupta, 2008). Although parametric testing procedure is also a possibility for testing the open ended responses (since the data is continuous), the study has chosen a non-parametric testing procedure to avoid assuming anything a priori about the true distribution of the parameter.

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The hypothesis to be tested is:

Ho: There is no significant difference in the exact MWTP responses between Group A and Group B

The test results from the Mann-Whitney U test is shown below :

Table 6: Mann-Whitney U Test Statistic between MWTP and Group

Mann-Whitney U	13009.500
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.127
Grouping Variable: Group	

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

Table 6 tells us that the test fails to reject the null hypothesis. This proves that there is no significant difference between the exact MWTP values of the two tested groups obtained from the open ended question. Open ended responses in a CVM study are expected to be more prone to biases because of no restriction on their upper limit. Respondents are free to state whatever they think to be appropriate to represent their preference for the good being valued. However, in this case, the open ended question was asked after the certainty scale question, which means it was also preceded by the reality check. So any possible difference in the MWTP values that might have been there was corrected out by the reality check and what we received was a set of hypothetical bias free MWTP values. With this, it can reasonably be expected that the influence of different levels of information also got minimised. This explains the result of the Mann-Whitney U test.

The conclusion drawn here is that the Mann-Whitney U test substantiates the results of the Pearson chi square test with HB corrected responses and provides a second line of defence to the argument that the WTP responses in the present study are free from information bias.

6.2 Comparison of WTP between respondents favouring Tax and VC: Presence of free riding results in underestimation of the WTP values. The study has selected the payment vehicles Tax and VC to test for this tendency. A tax being mandatory in nature is supposed to be less appealing to respondents with a tendency to free ride and hence given an option, they are more likely to choose a voluntary contribution over tax any day so that, they can skip making a payment or two whenever they can or at least minimise their payment whenever they can. So there is a fair chance that most of the free riders, (if there were any) would be

concentrated in the group VC. Since we know free riders have a tendency to understate their preference for a good, they are more likely to show a higher inclination towards saying 'no' (or a lower inclination towards saying 'yes') to an offered bid or state a lower MWTP value in comparison to their counterparts, although their true WTP may be equal to or greater than what is expressed by them. In this context, if there is a difference between the WTP responses of the respondents choosing VC and those choosing tax, it will indicate a presence of free riding behaviour. To test the presence of this tendency in the surveyed respondents, they were asked to choose one of these methods to make their payments for the proposed preservation plan. However, the respondents were also given an open ended option to name any other payment vehicle that they might want to go for instead of tax and VC. But none of the respondents were found reporting any other payment vehicle. The sample size for testing the presence of free riding has to be restricted to 326. This is because, the option to choose the preferred method of payment was provided only to those respondents who reported 'yes' to this initial question, "Would you be willing to pay a part of your monthly household income to implement the proposed preservation plan for DSNP, as it has just been described, for a period of five years?". A total of 36 respondents reported a 'no' to this question and missed the opportunity to choose the preferred payment vehicle. Hence they were excluded from the target sample for this case.

Table 12 provides an idea of the inter and intra group behaviours of the respondents.

Table 12: Distribution of responses to offered bids between respondents choosing Tax and respondents choosing VC

Answer Type (Response to offered bids)	Payment Vehicle		Total
	VC	Tax	
Yes	142 [58.4%] (74%)	101 [41.6%] (75.4%)	243 [100%]
No	50 [60.2%] (26%)	33 [39.8%] (24.6%)	83 [100%]
Total	192 (100%)	134 (100%)	326

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

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Note: Figures within [.] and (.) are percentages within Answer type and Payment Vehicle respectively

Out of 326 respondents, 192 have chosen VC as their preferred method of payment and 134 have chosen tax. Hence, VC is clearly the more preferred option between the two. But this alone is not enough to prove the presence of free riding. Out of the total 192 respondents from the VC group, 26% have answered 'no' to the offered bids while in the tax group, out of a total of 134, 24.6% have answered 'no'. No striking difference has been observed between the two groups here. In the total 83 'no' responses, the share of the VC group is 60.2% and that of the Tax group is 39.8%. So, the VC group figures more prominently in the 'no' responses. But this over representation can be attributed to the overall larger share of the group in the grand total, rather than to the tendency of free riding, since the same group also dominates the 'yes' responses (58.4%). So, the observations again are insufficient to prove the presence of free riding. However, to confirm these observations, a Pearson chi square test has been run to compare the WTP responses in keeping with the fact that the data are ordinal in nature. The null hypothesis to be tested for the Pearson chi square test is:

H₀: The distribution of responses between respondents preferring Tax and VC is the same.

The results of the Pearson chi square has been shown in table 13.

Table 13: Chi-Square Test results for responses and Payment vehicle

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	0.083	1	0.773
N of Valid Cases	326		

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

As expected, the test fails to reject the null hypothesis. Hence, there is no significant difference between the responses of the tax preferring respondents and their counterparts preferring VC. This finding fails to detect the presence of free riding behaviour.

To see if the scenario changes after the reality check, the same analysis has been repeated with the HB corrected responses.

Table 14: Distribution of HB corrected responses to offered bids between respondents choosing Tax and VC

Answer Type (HB Corrected Responses)	Payment Vehicle		Total
	VC	Tax	
Yes	98 [56%] (51%)	77 [44%] (57.5%)	175 [100%]
No	94 [62.3%] (49%)	57 [37.7%] (42.5%)	151 [100%]
Total	192 (100%)	134 (100%)	326

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

Note: Figures within [.] and (.) are percentages within Answer type and Payment Vehicle respectively

After the reality check, the number of 'no' responses in both the groups have increased in comparison to initial responses. In case of VC it increased from 50 to 94 and in case of Tax it increased from 33 to 57 (compared with table 12). Out of the total 151 'no' responses, the share of the VC group is still high at 62.3% and the share of the Tax group is 37.7%. But this again is not sufficient for showing the presence of free riding since, share of VC is also considerably high in the 'yes' responses (56%). Within Group, 49% of the respondents reported 'no' from the VC group, while 42.5% reported 'no' from the Tax group. The proportion seems to be slightly higher in case of VC than that of tax. But to see whether or not this difference is statistically significant, we need to perform the chi-square test with the hypothetical bias corrected responses.

Table 15: Chi-Square test results for HB corrected responses and payment vehicle

	Value	df	Asymp. Sig. (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	1.309	1	0.253
N of Valid Cases	326		

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

The results of table 15, fails to reject the null hypothesis and indicates no significant difference between the HB corrected responses of the two groups and suggests absence of free riding behaviour. To test whether or not the WTP responses of the open ended style also tell the same story, Mann-Whitney U test has been run. The hypothesis to be tested is:

H₀: There is no significant difference between the exact MWTP responses of the respondents preferring Tax and respondents preferring VC

The test results are depicted in table 16

Table 16: Mann-Whitney U Test Statistic between MWTP and Payment vehicle

	Maximum WTP
Mann-Whitney U	12479.000
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.634
Grouping Variable: Payment Vehicle	

Source: Author's computation from Field survey

The test once again matches the results of Pearson chi square and fails to reject the null hypothesis. It can hence be concluded that, there is no significant difference between the exact MWTP values of the two groups in question and hence no free riding behaviour. To understand the factors working behind selecting a particular payment vehicle, a question was put to the respondents asking about their principal motive for choosing Tax/VC. Most of the respondents preferring VC expressed that rather than contributing the money to the government exchequer, they would like to contribute it to NGOs working efficiently in that particular area since they believe that it will yield faster result, and that the NGOs have a

better scope for local participation and hence are easy to monitor. Thus a strong positive opinion towards NGOs has been found. The group favouring Tax mostly opined that a tax would actually be used for the purpose it is being collected and there won't be any chance of someone else snatching the money. These motives provide a reflection that their intentions to contribute for the proposed preservation plan are less likely to be guided by the tendency of free riding.

7. Conclusion:

The study was an attempt to test the validity of CVM against the backdrop of two important criticisms labelled on it. In the presence of a bias, the true WTP will not be revealed; rather it will either be overestimated or underestimated. Choosing such biased estimates for policy analysis can have misleading consequences. But in the absence of another versatile reliable alternative to measure preservation values, CVM still has an undeniable dominance in the valuation literature. Adopting appropriate corrective measures (both ex-ante and ex-post) in every possible step of a CVM study can reduce if not completely eliminate, the biases to a significant scale. The results of the current study also call for a similar line of thought. The final findings nullify the influence of information and free riding and provide answer to the research question that it is not inevitable for the WTP responses received via CVM to be affected by information bias and free riding. Free riding was altogether absent and information bias, although initially found present, could be corrected after taking care of hypothetical bias. The alternative tests performed in the study produced somewhat synchronised results which also strengthen the robustness of these findings. To conclude, it is reasonable to opine that correcting for hypothetical bias may prove to be a key to removing many other anomalies in CVM that are believed to arise from its hypothetical nature. The present study substantiates this statement. However, it will be too enthusiastic to claim that these results can be generalised. The importance of more experiments and investigations in this regard can never be undermined.

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